

Effect of Selective Aasana, Pranayam, Dhayan & Mudra Practices on Problem Solving Ability of Secondary Level Student

Mamta Bhardwaj

Assistant Professor, Dept. of Education

Dev Sanskriti Viswavidyalaya, Haridwar

Email: mamtab1312@gmail.com, Mob. No. 7417790865

Received : 03/11/2023

1st BPR : 20/11/2023

2nd BPR : 01/12/2023

Accepted : 09/12/2023

Abstract

These research paper indicate that regular practices of yogic package may useful increase problem solving ability. Therefore you can say that yogic practice effect psychological change. All studies indicate that it produces positive changes in cognitive ability. This technique relaxes body & empour mind. Hey it can be said as The end of study or research that "the Effect of selective yogic practices on Problem Solving Ability of secondary level student. The recent study had been complete with significant result.

Key words: Yogic Practices, Problem Solving Ability, Secondary level students

Introduction

The secrets of the inner world of life are yet to be uncovered. Through the regular practice of certain yogic techniques one can enhance his capacities not only physically but also mentally, socially and spiritually. In this way he can achieve holistic health, which can be utilized in any required field of the life. Certainly, In Professional field Yoga plays a vital role for the enhancement of the human recourse in holistic way.

In general, previous studies have revealed higher levels of attention, concentration, and memory for yoga practitioners than the non-practicing adolescents, Children who practice yoga enjoy better health, temperament, discipline, behavior, concentration, memory and stamina, mental ability. Due to technology or rote learning, the rest are not able to develop their mental ability and problem solving skills Children lack deep understanding Cognitive difficulties impede the student's overall daily functioning and personality development.

Furthermore, the word also becomes a hindrance in the adjustment process, likely leading to dissonance. Psychologists have discovered that there is no one right direction for studying cognition. All cognitive processes must be studied With the development of society and the improvement of the system, the problem of students with learning difficulties has become a concern of society, teachers and parents Areas of research in many disciplines address learning difficulties I did a cognitive boosting yoga set, what effect does it have on a child's mental abilities and problem solving skills Cognitive ability is often seen as an important predictor of job performance because it helps to understand the positive impact of training.

This is so because cognitive abilities demonstrate two of the most critical abilities needed to perform well in any job. It includes the ability to learn and absorb information as well as to apply what you learn to solve problems and act quickly. Improved job performance is directly related to high cognitive ability.

Objective

To find out the effect of yogic practices on problem solving ability of secondary level students.

Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1 : There is no significant effect of pre and post practice of selective yogic practice on Problem Solving Ability of Secondary level Students.

Hypothesis 2 : There is no significant effect of post practice of selective yogic practice of on Problem solving Ability of girls and boys of secondary level students.

Delimitation

1. The study was conducted for the period of 6 weeks.
2. The study was delimited to the age ranging from 13 to 15 years.
3. The research work was delimited to the 20 students secondary level student group from the respective government school.

Research Methodology

Experimental research establishes a relationship between the causal and effect of a situation. It is a causal design. where we observe the impact caused by the independent Variable on the dependent.

Research Design

In this present study single groups pre-post design is used.

Sample and Sampling

The research work included 20 samples which were selected by Purposive (non Probability sampling) Sampling method. The data was collected in my dissertation my population dividing in a scale on the basis of age, class research and environment according work to my research work and students of age group 12 to 15.

Sample (20)

Boys 10 and Girls 10

This practice will given for 40 days.

Research Tool

Problem Solving Ability Test

It was made by L.N. Dubey (Jabalpur)

There are 20 items each has 4 alternative. Scoring of text is done with the help of Proctored keys.

Procedure for data collection

In this present study single groups pre-post design is used. 20 subjects were taken who were the students of Bahadradabad, Haridwar between age 12 to 15 year. The pre post test of all the subjects of the group were taken by Mental & ability and Problem solving Ability. After taking the pre-test subjects were given into the practice to yoga package for 40 days for 30 min daily in the evening After 40 days post-test was administered. The data obtained from the pre and post tests statistically analyzed by using t-test.

Yogic Intervention

Time duration for yogic practice	- 40 days.
Prayer gayatri mantra	- 5 min.
Practice of virkshasana	- 5 min .
practice of Bharamare Pranayama	- 5 min
Practice of Ganesh/Hakini mudra	- 3-3 min.
Trataka	- 5 min.

Statistical technique

The data obtained from the pre and post tests statistically analyzed by using t-test.

Statistical Analytical Table

Hypothesis 1:- There is no significant effect of pre and post practice of selective yogic practice on Problem Solving Ability of Secondary level Students

Total no of students	Stage	Mean	SD	SED	T-Value	d.f	Significant level
20	Pre	8.35	2.16	0.518	7.7206	19	0.05 & 0.01
20	Post	12.35	2.66				

Hypothesis 2:- There is no significant effect of post practice of selective yogic practice of on Problem solving Ability of girls and boys of secondary level students.

Total no of students	stage	Mean	SD	SED	T-Value	d.f	Significant level
10 Boys	post	8.50	2.12	0.522	8.6248	9	0.05 & 0.01
10 Girls	post	13.00	2.98				

Interpretation of the Result

Table (1), Shows the mean value are 8.35 for pre fest and 12.35 for post test and the t-value is 7.720 6 which is more then the required value of 2.861 at df = 19 on 0.01 level and 2.093 at df=19 on 0.05 level.This proves that mean difference is highly significant that's why our null hypotheses is got rejected .

Table 2,Show the mean value 8.50 for pre test of boys and 13.00 for post test of boys and t-value is 8.6248 of boys which is more then the required value 3.250 at df=9 on 0.01 level and 2.262 at df =9 on 0.05 level This proves that mean difference is highly significant. that's why our null hypothesis is got rejected.

Discusion of the Study

“Effect of Selective Asana,Pranayam, Dhayan & Mudra Practices on Problem solving ability of Secondary level student.”

In this study research has taken 20 students, who are within 12-15 Age group are selected purposive Sampling and used pre and post research design. The duration of my study is 40 days and Yogic practices are effective on cognitive ability. We apply yogic practices on only normal students.we get good results from subjects . So there is a significant effect of yogic practices on cognitive ability.

Statically it is found that there is significant difference in the level of Cognitive ability. Asana, Pranayam, mantra, tratak, Ganesh mudra are beneficial for physiological as well as Psychological imbalance for the student.

After doing practice of this specific. Yogic practices, it is found that this is important practice Asana makes their body flexible and pranayam controls the emotions. Tratak increase, concentration power, Because this practice regulates the nervous system So in this research work it found that if subjects will continue this practice regularly they will become strong physically well as emotionally.

Yogic Practices used to enhance The over all personality of Students with all aspect of their life. self confidence is one of the required power for the people specially for the students with respect to their

memory. concentration and many more. Mental conflicts for achieving their ultimate goal with the day to day activities.

Yoga is the art and science of living, and is concerned with the development of mind and body. Therefore, yoga includes systematic disciplines for the all-round development of a person in a coordinated manner. We often begin the yogic disciplines with the outer dimension of personality, the physical body.

Pranayama with asanas directly affects the brain and the endocrine system, that is, the child's mind and its emotions. It helps to restore emotional harmony and psychomotor normality, that is, a state of normal attention. Yoga is clearly a method of holistic education that can be used on all children, as it develops physical energy, emotional stability, and intellectual and creative talents. It is an integrated method of balanced development of the overall personality of the child. In yoga, the top gland is considered to be related to the Ajna Chakra. Mystics and occultists call it the third eye, while philosophers have named it the supermind. In young children, the apex gland remains very active, but by the time it reaches eight to ten years of age, it starts to decay, and it has almost no role in the life of adults. Because in yoga, the top gland is considered the controlling and enlightening center of the brain. Another important thing that I clearly understood was that the adrenal glands influence the moral behavior of the child in a significant way. Generally, people with criminal tendencies have an overactive adrenal system. This fact has an important place in the education of children.

Children should be made to practice mantra for the development of memory. Mantras immediately become active on the subconscious and unconscious levels of the mind. Clear memory can be developed in children with the help of mantra, intuition and yoganidra.

- by Swami Satyananda Saraswati

Conclusion

Yoga, the upheaval of emotions is the result of imbalance of Manas Shakti and Prana Shakti. When the child has excess of mental energy and lack of prana, he does not take interest in anything and is surrounded by depression, anxiety or lethargy. He lacks dynamism and is unable to convert his mental energy into creative activities. On the contrary, if the child has an excess of Prana and a deficiency of Manas, he will become extremely destructive and disruptive

References

- Saraswati (1994) : Bacho ke liye yog siksha (Vol. 1) [Hindi]. Yog publication trust munger. <https://www.biharyoga.net>.
- Wikipedia contributors. (2022) : Gheranda Samhita. Wikipedia. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gheranda_Samhita.
- Effectiveness of Yoga on Memory of Learners in Secondary Level. (2020) : International Journal of. Recent Technology and Engineering. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijrte.e5853.018520>
- Girdhar, M. (2014) : Problem solving ability of adolescents with respect to the locus of control, gender and locality. (n.d.). <http://www.jiarm.com/jan/>.
- TANDON, R.K., (1957) : Mental Testing: Study of general mental Un published Ph. D. thesis, Varanasi, B.H.U. ability of college adult, Unpublished Ph.D.thesis, Varanasi. B.H.U.
- Vivekanand Rishi (2006) : Practical Yoga Psychology. Bihar. Yoga Publication Trust.<http://www.experiencefestival.com/a/shat-karma/id/23908>
- Singh (2002) : Trataka vibration produce significance effect upon Hypothalamus & pituitary gland. Retrieved from
- Wikipedia, memory (2005) : Retrieved from <http/en.Wikipedia.org/wiki/memory>. page 1 of 4.
- Saraswati, S.(2004) : Dharend samhita, Saraswati S.S.Yoga bharti Munger,Bhiar
- Swami, Saraswati. S.(2005) : Asana Pranayama Mudra bandha. Yoga publication trust, Munger, Bihar, Page-115.

